

eolus®

Welcome to Malmö!

VindKraftNet, November 2025

This is Eolus today

Portfolio of 26.2 GW

Portfolio by Technology Q2 2025 (MW)

- Onshore wind
- Offshore wind
- Solar
- Storage

Total **26,198 MW**

Portfolio by Development Phase Q2 2025 (MW)

We create value at every step of the way with our core asset-light business model

Looking forward to today's discussions!

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